

DESIGN AND THERMODYNAMIC SIMULATION OF A SOLAR ABSORPTION ICEMAKER

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ABSTRACT

A solar absorption icemaker was designed. It is an intermittent system and uses Calcium Chloride and Ammonia as absorbent and refrigerant respectively. The single glazed collector/absorber/generator unit uses a plane glass sheet as the outer cover. Overall collector plate exposed area is 1.0m². A thermodynamic simulation of the icemaker has been performed in order to investigate the effect that the generator temperature and collector efficiency have over the Coefficient of Performance (COP). The average solar coefficient of performance of the system is 0.78. It was found that for a constant efficiency at the solar collector, there is an optimum temperature to be used as the generator temperature.

KEY WORDS: Solar energy, simulation, absorption, ammonia, calcium chloride, icemaker

NOMENCLATURE

Q_p (W) – Heat gain produced by occupants

Q_w (W) – Latent heat gain brought by moisture gain

A_i (m²) – surface area of a part of building structure overall

U_i (W/m²K) – heat transfer coefficient

T_{cool} (hrs) – time of cooling per day

k_j (W/mK) – heat conductivity of the material of j – th layer according to air

m – mass flow rate

h – enthalpy

coefficient of performance

T – temperature

η – efficiency

g – acceleration due to gravity

η – Collector efficiency

COP – Coefficient of performance

INTRODUCTION

The climatic profile, socio-economic development and energy supply infrastructures in Kano indicate a high demand for cooling applications and strongly suggest the use of solar and renewable energy powered systems. Cold storage of food products and medicines, especially immunization vaccines, are important application of solar refrigeration. Many agricultural products like fruits, vegetables, meat, fish etc., can be maintained in fresh conditions for significantly longer period of time if they are stored at low temperatures. At present in Kano large quantities of these products are lost annually due to poor storage facilities. This situation is even worse in the remote rural areas where these fresh food materials are produced. As a result sharp differences in food supplies

exist between the harvest and off harvest periods. High market value agricultural products are usually abundant and cheap during the harvest season and expensive at other times. Solar refrigeration can assist to reverse this trend.

Solar powered refrigeration has been very attractive during the last twenty years, since the availability of sunshine and the needs for refrigeration both reach maximum level in the same season. One of the most effective forms of solar refrigeration is the production of ice, as ice can accumulate much latent heat, thus the size of the icemaker can be made small (Sumathy,1999).

Absorption refrigeration relies on the absorption of a refrigerant gas into an absorbent at low pressure and subsequent desorption by heating. Solar absorption icemaker consists of a solar collector, a condenser and an evaporator that is placed in a refrigeration box.

The solar absorption cycle is similar to the mechanical vapour compression cycle in that it employs volatile refrigerant, which alternately under low pressure in the evaporator vapourizes by absorbing latent heat from the material being cooled and condenses under high pressure in the condenser by surrendering the latent heat to the condensing medium.

DESIGN OF SYSTEM AND COMPONENTS

Many absorbent/refrigerant combinations have been designed in the past, either experimentally or commercially. These include $\text{CaCl}_2/\text{NH}_3$, $\text{SrCl}_2/\text{NH}_3$, $\text{LiNO}_3/\text{NH}_3$, NaSCN/NH_3 , $\text{LiBr}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, glycol ether/R21, with the most popular being $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{NH}_3$. The absorbents, particularly in the first four above, are able to generate large quantities of refrigerant, such as HN_3 , at low temperatures of the order of 100°C , making it possible for low temperature heat sources, such as waste heat and solar thermal radiation, to be used.

In reference (Iloje, 1995) a comparison was made between $\text{CaCl}_2/\text{NH}_3$, $\text{SrCl}_2/\text{NH}_3$ and $\text{LiNO}_3/\text{NH}_3$, $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{NH}_3$, NaSCN/NH_3 systems. Operating conditions were assumed to be 40°C ambient temperature, 0.55-0.45 solar collector efficiency, 5 h generation, 12 h absorption, and a total radiant flux of 1040 W/m^2 . The tests shows the superiority of the solid absorbents over the liquid absorbents, with CaCl_2 being slightly better (and cheaper) than SrCl_2 .

2.1 DESIGN PARAMETERS

Solar radiation	931 w/m^2
Ambient temperature (outside)	32°C
Ambient (Room) temperature	28°C
Condensing temperature	37°C
Evaporating temperature	-10°C
Collector/generator temperature	100°C
Final ice temperature	-5°C
Generation period	6hrs
Absorption period	12hrs
Evaporator water mass	4kg
Refrigerant/absorbent pair	Ammonia/calcium chloride

From reference data for Kano, the average daily solar radiation for the 12 months calendar year is 26.83 MJ/m^2 (Musbahu,2008) Assuming that our design 6hr day solar radiation which is about 75% of the daily value is uniformly distributed through out the 6 hours period; hence 931 W/m^2 was estimated.

Ammonia can evaporate at temperature below 0°C . In fact evaporating temperature of -12°C had been achieved for liquid absorbent systems (Farber, 1970). Consequently, an evaporating temperature of -10°C and evaporator water temperature of -5°C was considered reasonable for sizing the system. A passive evaporative condenser constructed for the system. A passive evaporative condenser constructed for the system (Neilson,1977) gave a temperature of

6°C below ambient, under humid condition. Assuming a condenser temperature of 5°C above ambient, a condensing temperature of 37°C was estimated, assuming an ambient temperature of 32°C.

Simulated absorption/generation test in (Iloeje, 1995) showed that 5h generation and 11h absorption were enough to produce 80% of maximum possible generation and absorption. 6hrs and 12h were therefore chosen for the generation and absorption periods for the system respectively.

THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES

ABSORPTION AND GENERATION PROCESSES OF Calcium chloride

The reaction of calcium chloride and ammonia are as given below:

The equilibrium reaction temperature – pressure curves (T – P curves) are given in figure (2) for equations i and ii and iii. At condensing temperature of 37°C, P₃ = 13.5 bar, T₃ = 90° C and T₂ = 100°C at an evaporating temperature of –10°C, P₃ = 3 bar, T₃ = 53° C and T₂ = 63°C.

Reaction (i) occurs at temperatures beyond those possible in flat plate collectors. Thus, 8 moles of NH₃ may be absorbed per mole of CaCl₂ during initial charging, but only 6 moles will be available for refrigeration. We shall assume no heat and pressure losses in components and lines. In order to analyse the system, mass and energy balance is performed at each components

Fig. 1.0 Schematic Diagram of Calcium chloride – ammonia Refrigeration Cycle

ENERGY BALANCE OF THE SYSTEM

Component	Calculation	Energy (Watt)	
		Gain	Losses
Evaporator	Total cooling load as calculated	24.70	–
Condenser	$\dot{Q}_c = \dot{m}_{ref} (h_1 - h_2)$	–	25.57
Generator	$\dot{Q}_g = \dot{m}_{ref} (h_1 - h_4)$	0.871	–
Balance		25.57	25.57

The schematic diagram of the absorption refrigerator assembly is as shown in Fig. 1.0. It consists of a combined collector/absorber/generator of collector plate actual area 1.25m² and effective exposed collector area of 1m². The collector plate was of galvanized corrugated sheets with 76mm corrugation pitch, and painted with black oil paint. There were two collector tubes, each of 59mm od x 54mm i.d. x 1000mm long galvanized steel pipe. The collector tubes were painted with black oil paint. The annular space between the inner and outer tubes was charged with 1.0 kg of absorber granules per tube, which occupied about 80% to 85% of the annular volume.

The collector plate and tubes assembly was mounted on the rear plate insulation inside a galvanized steel box. Its glazing was a clear plane glass. The insulation consists of 50.8mm thick expanded polystyrene chips. The collector/absorber/generator component was inclined at the latitude of 12.05° (which is that of Kano), was supported at its base and raised 1m above the ground level on an angle iron support frame.

In a low pressure system, such as the one designed, the condenser and the evaporator must necessarily be closed to each other and the collector. Thus, they are located directly under the collector/generator/absorber unit such that the refrigerant flows into them is by gravity. The condenser steel piping is 7.18m length of 21mm od x 18mm id coiled. It is of galvanized steel tube.

The separate evaporator consisted of a spirally coiled 21mm od x 18mm id tube galvanized steel tube of total length 1.13m. The liquid receiver and the evaporator vessel placed inside separate box of inside dimensions 300mm wide x 300mm breadth x 300mm high x 50.8mm thick. The gap was filled with expanded polystyrene insulation. The box or the ice cabinet was made up of galvanized metal sheets as the out side wall, while aluminum sheets were used as the inner walls in order to reduce transmission and absorption of heat. The design was carried out in Kano, Nigeria using the locally available materials. Solar and other relevant data used during the design were also of Kano.

Simulation Analysis

Mathematical model

Figure 1.0 illustrates the main components of the solid absorption icemaker. In order to analyse the system, mass and energy balances were performed at each component. For the current study, it is assumed that the refrigerant vapour is 100% ammonia.

At the expansion,

$$\dot{m}_2 = \dot{m}_3 = \dot{m}_{ref} \text{ (Total mass balance)}$$

And

$$h_2 = h_3 \text{ (Energy balance)}$$

At the evaporator,

$$\dot{m}_3 = \dot{m}_4 = \dot{m}_{ref}$$

$$Q_e = \dot{m}_{ref} (h_4 - h_3)$$

Or,

$$\dot{m}_{ref} = \frac{Q_e}{h_4 - h_3}$$

At the condenser,

$$\dot{m}_1 = \dot{m}_2 \text{ (Total mass balance)}$$

$$\dot{Q}_c = \dot{m}_{ref} (h_1 - h_2)$$

At the generator

$$\dot{m}_4 = \dot{m}_1 \text{ (Mass balance)}$$

$$\dot{Q}_g = \dot{m}_1 h_1 - \dot{m}_4 - h_4$$

$$Q_g = m_{ref} (h_1 - h_4)$$

The COP of the absorption system is given by

$$COP = \frac{Q_e}{Q_g}$$

Computational model

In order to analyze how the system react to different operating conditions, its necessary to simulate the variables that effect its performance, with the intention of obtaining the maximum COP out of the system. The operating conditions choose were:

$$T_g = 70 - 140^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_c = 37^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_a = 32^\circ\text{C}$$

$$T_e = -10^\circ\text{C}$$

Refrigerant mass flow mref = 0.000022746kg/s

From Antonio, (2006) the liquid and vapour enthalpies of the refrigerant NH₃ can be calculated from equations 1 and 2 respectively.

$$h_l(T) = \sum_{i=0}^3 b_i (T - 27.15)^i \tag{1}$$

$$h_v(T) = \sum_{i=0}^3 c_i (T - 27.15)^i \tag{2}$$

The coefficients for equations 1 & 2 are presented in the table 2.0 below

Table 2.0 coefficients for equations 1 – 2 (Antonio, 2006)

I	b_i	c_i
0	1.99E+02	1.46E+03
1	4.46E+00	1.28E+00
2	6.28E-03	-0.011501
3	1.46E-04	-0.00021523
4	-1.5262E-06	1.91E-06
5	-1.8069E-08	2.56E-08
6	1.91E-10	-2.5964E-10

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The operating boundaries of the system were examined by conducting simulations for various values of generator temperature, T_g , the operating ranges were $70^\circ\text{C} < T_g < 140^\circ\text{C}$. The results were showed in Fig. 2.0 represents the COP Vs generator temperature for 100% efficiencies at the collector for a fixed evaporator temperature and condenser temperature. It shows that the COP increases as the generator temperature increases and the COP approaches uniformity as the generator temperature continue to increase. This may be explained by the fact that all the absorbed ammonia was separated from the calcium chloride and thus no more refrigerant flow to the condenser.

Fig. 2.0 COP variation as a function of generator temperature for 100% efficiency at the Collector

Fig. 3.0 COP variation as a function of the generator temperature for 75% collector efficiency

Fig. 4.0 COP variation as a function of the generator temperature for 50% collector efficiency

Fig. 5.0 COP variations as a function of the generator temperature for different values of collector efficiency

The system COP for 75% efficiency at the solar collector for fixed evaporator temperature and condenser temperature is depicted in fig. 3.0. The system COP decreases as the generator temperature increases. It reaches minimum and then increases progressively as the generator temperature continues to increase. This may be explained by the fact that the generator temperatures corresponding the decreased COPs are below desorption temperature for the solid absorption refrigeration cycle, as such it is at the absorption phase of ammonia gas by the absorbent.

Fig. 4.0 shows that the COP decreases as the generator temperature increases for a greater portion of the chart and then later starts to increase. This may be explained by the same manner above. The increase in COP means that more heat was absorbed in the evaporator. In other words, full amount of refrigerant is absorbed during absorption.

The generator temperature effects over the system COP for different efficiencies at the solar collector is shown in fig. 5.0. The chart can be described as follows;
 For a given generator temperature; the system COP increases as the efficiency augment.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Ammonia – calcium chloride solar absorption icemaker was designed and constructed. The refrigeration cycle was analyzed with their thermodynamic properties expressed in polynomial equations. The coefficient of performance (COP) of the cycle versus the generator temperature at different collector efficiencies was analysed and it was noticed that the collector efficiency is an important factor to consider for the optimum temperature at which the solar absorption cycle operates. The collector efficiency determines the maximum temperature that should be used at the generator in order to achieve the maximum COP out of the system. The COP obtained were in the range of 0.78 – 0.83 which are in agreement with what was obtained by Nelson et al (1977) which gave a COP of 0.75. Also an experimentally based simulation model of a solar powered water chiller reported in Best et al (1992) gave the cycle COP as 0.75. Other activities on solid absorption refrigerators reported in Worsoe (1983), give the cycle COPs in the range of 0.4 – 0.8. These previous results validate what is obtained in this simulation analysis. The simulation was carried out on specific temperatures at the generator, condenser and the generator.

A lot of research and development are needed to prove the economic viability of solar absorption ice making technology using locally available materials, in order to compete favourably with vapour compression refrigeration systems.

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